

A Performance Evaluation of Intrusion Detection by Fuzzy Possibilistic C-Means Clustering Algorithm over the NSL-KDD Dataset

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Abstract— IDS is a procedure of observing the events happening in a computer system or network and analyzing them for indication of a conceivable potential event which is an infringement or inevitable dangers of infringement or computer security approaches or standard security strategies of adjacent threats. MATLAB 2018a tool is used for the implementation on a NSL-KDD dataset. The motivation behind this investigation is to detect the attack. This paper, deals with the evaluation of data mining based machine learning algorithms viz. Fuzzy C-Means and Fuzzy Possibilistic C-Means clustering algorithms to identify intrusion over NSL-KDD dataset for effectively detecting the major attack categories i.e. DoS, R2L, U2R and Probe.

Keywords— IDS, NSL-KDD Dataset, MATLAB, Fuzzy C-Means Algorithm, Fuzzy possibilistic C-Means Algorithm.

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to the rapid growth in the technology and widespread use of the Internet, a lot of problems have been faced to secure the system's critical information within or across the networks because there are millions of people attempting to attack on systems to extract critical information. A huge number of attacks have been observed in the last few years [1].

IDS provide three important security tasks to monitor, detect, and respond to unauthorized activities [2]. It can be exploited by either non authorized or authorized users. Several tools are being designed and implemented for a variety of exploitations in diverse range of security attacks. Among these tools is the intrusion detection systems (IDS) which allow us to monitor a range of computer systems: an information system, a network or a cloud computing. These IDS identify intrusions and characterized as endeavors to break the security goals, for example, privacy, integrity and accessibility and non-denial [3].

The remaining articles have been organized in the following form. Fuzzy C-means are discussed in section II, then section III talks about relevant tasks for our experiment. Section III presents the design and definition used. Section IV provides and discusses the test results of the experiment. Section V presents the experiment conclusions.

II. FUZZY C-MEANS

Fuzzy clustering is a powerful unsupervised method for the analysis of data and construction of models. Fuzzy c-means algorithm is most generally utilized. The FCM [4] utilizes fuzzy partitioning to such an extent that a data point

can have a place with all gatherings with various membership grades in the range of 0 and 1.

The algorithm is implemented in MATLAB environment with the following objective function:

$$Z = \sum_{i=0}^n \sum_{j=1}^c u_{ij}^m \|x_i - c_j\|^2 \quad (1)$$

Where, m is any real no., whose value lies between $1 \leq m \leq \infty$, u_{ij} is the degree of membership of x_i in the cluster j , x_i is the i^{th} value of n dimensional calculated data, c_j is the center of dimension of the cluster.

In cluster center matrix c "(1)" has been randomly introduced and fuzzy partition matrix U has been created, which is created through the iterative optimization of the above mentioned objective function, which is shown by the subscription of membership u_{ij} and the cluster centers c_j are as follows:

$$u_{ij} = \frac{1}{\sum_{k=1}^c \left(\frac{\|x_i - c_j\|}{\|x_i - c_k\|} \right)^{\frac{2}{m-1}}} \quad (2)$$

$$C_j = \sum_{i=1}^n (u_{ij})^m x_i / \sum_{i=1}^n (u_{ij})^m \quad (3)$$

This iteration will stop when, $\|u(k+1) - u(k)\| < \epsilon$

Where value of ϵ lies between 0 and 1 and closed to 0 and k is the iteration number.

The stepwise algorithm is as per the following:

Step 1: Initially $U = [u_{ij}]$ matrix, $U^{(0)}$

Step 2: At k -step, compute the centers vectors

$$C_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (u_{ij})^m x_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n (u_{ij})^m} \quad (4)$$

Step 3: Update $u^{(k)}$, $u^{(k+1)}$

$$u_{ij} = \frac{1}{\sum_{k=1}^c \left(\frac{\|x_i - c_j\|}{\|x_i - c_k\|} \right)^{\frac{2}{m-1}}} \quad (5)$$

Step 4: If $\|u^{(k+1)} - u^{(k)}\| < \epsilon$ then STOP; otherwise return to step 2.

In FCM, data are appointed to every cluster with the assistance of a membership function which is utilized to speak to the fuzzy behaviour of this algorithm. FCM can be used for network intrusion detection as an efficient technique [5].

III. LITERATURE SURVEY

Partha Sarathi Bhattacharjee et al. (2017) This paper, deals with the evaluation of data mining based machine learning algorithms viz. K-Means and Fuzzy C-Means clustering

algorithms to identify intrusion over NSL-KDD dataset for effectively detecting the major attack categories i.e. DoS, R2L, U2R and Probe[5].

Dikshant Gupta et al. (2016) this research paper involves applying various data mining algorithms, which include linear regression and k-mine clustering, which automatically generate rules for classifying network activities. A comparative analysis of these techniques has also been done to detect intrusion. To learn the patterns of the attacks, NSL-KDD dataset has been used [6].

Anand Keshri et al. (2016) discuss about DOS attacks and briefly view the different prevention schemes. Then we discussed various methods of IDS using DoS Prevention and Data Mining techniques while using firewalls and IDS. We used the NSL-KDD dataset, a sophisticated version of the kdd'99 cup data set for applying and testing data mining algorithms [7].

Ketan Sanjay Desale et al. (2015) present the mechanism to enhance the proficiency of the IDS utilizing streaming data mining procedure. We apply four chose stream information classification algorithms on NSL-KDD datasets and contrast their outcomes. In light of the similar examination of their outcomes best strategy is discovered for efficiency enhancement of IDS [8].

Tanya Garg and Surinder Singh Khurana (2014) present the comparative performance of NSL-KDD based data set compatible classification algorithms. These classifications have been evaluated in the WEKA environment using the 41 attributes. About 94,000 examples of complete KDD datasets are included in the training data set and over 48,000 examples are included in the test data set. Garrett's Ranking Technique has been applied to rank different classifiers according to their performance. Rotation Forest classification approach outperformed the rest [9].

Sait Murat GIRAY and Aydn Goze POLAT (2013) in this study, normal and noisy datasets for network IDS domain are used and various classification algorithms are evaluated. Results show that evaluation of algorithms without noise is confusing for IDS because the best performing algorithms of no-noise are not necessarily identical in realistic noise environments. Moreover refined NSL KDD dataset allows a more realistic evaluation of various algorithms than the original KDD 99 dataset [10].

Hind Tribak et al. (2012) implement different learning algorithms on the NSL- KDD data set, which identify between normal and attack connections and compare their performance in different scenarios- for classification considerations, features selection and algorithmic method - Using a powerful statistical analysis: ANOVA. In this study, the complexity of computational time and methodology is analyzed for the accuracy of configuration of both different systems and operating systems [11].

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

A. Problem Statement

Fuzzy c-means (FCM) algorithm is one of the important clustering techniques. However, it is sensitive to noises and is easily struck at local minima and not detects the attacks at

high percentage. To overcome the drawbacks of FCM, Pal and Bezdek proposed a new clustering technique called Fuzzy possibilistic c-means algorithm (FPCM).

B. Fuzzy Possibilistic C- Means

Pal and Bezdek [12] define a clustering algorithm, which is called FPCM [13], which combines characteristics of both fuzzy and possibilistic c-means. Memberships and specificity are important for data substrate in clustering problems. As a representation, an objective function based on both membership and specificity in the FPCM:

$$\text{Minimize } J_{FPCM} = \sum_{i=1}^c \sum_{j=1}^n (u_{ij}^m + t_{ij}^\eta) d_{ij}^2 \quad (6)$$

With the following constraints

$$\sum_{i=1}^c u_{ij} = 1, \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n t_{ij} = 1, \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq c \quad (8)$$

The Fuzzy possibilistic c-means algorithm is given below:

Step 1: Given data object X, fix ϵ , c , $2 \leq c \leq n$, $m > 1$, $\eta > 1$, $0 \leq u_{ij}$, $t_{ij} \leq 1$ and initialize the membership function values $U_{ij}(0)$ and $t_{ij}(0)$, $1 \leq i \leq c$; $1 \leq j \leq n$, at step t, $t = 0, 1, 2, \dots, t_{\max}$

Step 2: Calculate the cluster centers

$$V_{ij}^{(t)} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (u_{ij}^m + t_{ij}^\eta) X_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n (u_{ij}^m + t_{ij}^\eta)} \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq c \quad (9)$$

Step 3: Calculate Euclidian distance

$$(d_{ij})^2 = \|X_j - V_i\|^2 \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq c; 1 \leq j \leq n \quad (10)$$

Step 4: Calculate the new membership values $U^{(t+1)}$ and typicality values $t^{(t+1)}$ to satisfy

$$U_{ij}^{(t+1)} = \frac{1}{\sum_{k=1}^c \left(\frac{d_{ij}^2}{d_{ik}^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{m-1}}} \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq c; 1 \leq j \leq n \quad (11)$$

$$t_{ij}^{(t+1)} = \frac{1}{\sum_{k=1}^c \left(\frac{d_{ij}^2}{d_{ki}^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{\eta-1}}} \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq c; 1 \leq j \leq n \quad (12)$$

Step 5: If $\|U^{(t+1)} - U^{(t)}\| \leq \epsilon$, then stop; otherwise $t = t+1$ and return to step 2.

C. Proposed Algorithm

- step 1: Load NSL-KDD Dataset.
- step 2: Preprocessed the dataset
 - 1) Nominal values replaced by Numeric values.
 - 2) Categorized the attacks.
- step 3: Normalize the features.
- step 4: Apply FPCM
 - 1) Given data object X, fix ϵ , c , $2 \leq c \leq n$, $m > 1$, $\eta > 1$, $0 \leq u_{ij}$, $t_{ij} \leq 1$ and initialize the membership function values $U_{ij}(0)$ and $t_{ij}(0)$, $1 \leq i \leq c$; $1 \leq j \leq n$, at step t, $t = 0, 1, 2, \dots, t_{\max}$
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$$V_{ij}^{(t)} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (u_{ij}^m + t_{ij}^\eta) X_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n (u_{ij}^m + t_{ij}^\eta)} \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq c$$

3) Compute Euclidian distance

$$(d_{ij})^2 = \|X_j - V_i\|^2 \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq c; 1 \leq j \leq n$$

4) Calculate the new membership values $U^{(t+1)}$ and typicality values $t^{(t+1)}$ to satisfy

$$U_{ij}^{(t+1)} = \frac{1}{\sum_{k=1}^c \left(\frac{d_{ij}^2}{d_{ik}^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{m-1}}} \quad \text{for } 1 \leq i \leq c; 1 \leq j \leq n$$

$$t_{ij}^{(t+1)} = \frac{1}{\sum_{k=1}^n \left(\frac{d_{ij}^2}{d_{ki}^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{\eta-1}}} \quad \text{for } 1 \leq i \leq c; 1 \leq j \leq n$$

5) If $\|U^{(t+1)} - U^{(t)}\| \leq \epsilon$, then stop; otherwise $t = t+1$ and return to (2).

step 5: Process will be continuing up to 4 Iteration.

step 6: Find the % of attack detected.

V. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP & RESULT ANALYSIS

In the present work, experimentations are carried out in MATLAB software platform to identify network intrusions. For identifying intrusions, Fuzzy C-Means and Fuzzy Possibilistic C-Means algorithms are employed over the NSL-KDD dataset. NSL-KDD dataset with a large amount of real time quality data is used for training and testing of intrusion detection. The NSL-KDD dataset is a better version of the KDD CUP99 dataset.

In this paper, an analysis of NSL-KDD dataset is made using data mining based algorithms like Fuzzy C-Means and Fuzzy Possibilistic C-Means clustering algorithms. Different types of attacks in NSL-KDD datasets are described in Table 1.

TABLE 1. Different Types of Attack in NSL-KDD Dataset

Category	Attack Type
Normal	Normal
DOS	Smurf, Back, Neptune, Teardrop, Pod, Land
U2R	Buffer_overflow, loadmodule, Rootkit, perl
R2L	Warezclient, Warezmaster, Guess_passwd, lmap, ftp_write, Multihop, Phf, Spy
Probe	Probe Satan, Portsweep, Ipsweep, Nmap

The experimental results of attack detection on NSL-KDD 20 percent dataset with 42 features using FPCM algorithm in MATLAB environment is shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2. The Detection of Attack by Fuzzy Possibilistic C-Means Clustering Algorithm for NSL-KDD 20 Percent Dataset with 42 Features (1st Iteration)

Cluster	Attack Category					No. of attacks detected	% of attack detection
	Normal	DOS	Probe	R2L	U2R		
1	172	62	59	3	5	301	1.194824
2	26	857	1037	1	0	1921	7.625437
3	2400	798	7801	187	4	11190	44.418863
4	10852	572	337	17	2	11780	46.760876

The Table 2 shows the percentage of attack detection for 4 clusters and found that maximum of 46.76% attack is detected for Cluster-4 in 1st iteration.

TABLE 3. The Detection of Attack by Fuzzy Possibilistic C-Means Clustering Algorithm for NSL-KDD 20 Percent Dataset with 42 Features (2nd Iteration)

Cluster	Attack Category					No. of attacks detected	% of attack detection
	Normal	DOS	Probe	R2L	U2R		
1	12459	903	457	173	10	14002	55.581137
2	570	1174	1392	11	0	3147	12.492061
3	91	1	17	23	0	132	0.523976
4	330	211	7368	1	1	7911	31.402826

From Table 3, it is found that maximum of 55.58% attack is detected in Cluster-1 in 2nd iteration.

TABLE 4. The Detection of Attack by Fuzzy Possibilistic C-Means Clustering Algorithm for NSL-KDD 20 Percent Dataset with 42 Features (3rd Iteration)

Cluster	Attack Category					No. of attacks detected	% of attack detection
	Normal	DOS	Probe	R2L	U2R		
1	140	108	3171	4	0	3423	13.587647
2	12735	897	546	192	10	14380	57.081613
3	242	28	146	2	1	419	1.663226
4	333	1256	5371	10	0	6970	27.667513

Table 4 shows the percentage of attack detection among four clusters by Fuzzy POSSIBILISTIC C-Means clustering algorithm for NSL-KDD 20 percent Dataset with 42 features is in 3rd iteration and maximum of 57.08% attack is detected in Cluster-2.

TABLE 5. Attack Detection by Fuzzy Possibilistic C-Means Clustering Algorithm for NSL-KDD 20 Percent Dataset with 42 Features (4th Iteration)

Cluster	Attack Category					No. of attacks detected	% of attack detection
	Normal	DOS	Probe	R2L	U2R		
1	28	8	33	3	0	72	0.285805
2	51	1264	8283	10	0	9608	38.139092
3	12444	867	366	188	9	13874	55.073039
4	927	150	552	7	2	1638	6.502064

Table 5 shows the maximum percentage of attack detection by Fuzzy Possibilistic C-Means Clustering Algorithm for NSL-KDD 20 percent Dataset with 42 features is 55.07%, which is detected for Cluster-3.

The summary table of Experimental results obtained with FPCM for NSL-KDD 20 Percent dataset with 42 features is presented in Table 6.

TABLE 6. Results of Fuzzy Possibilistic C-Means for NSL-KDD 20 Percent Dataset with 42 Features

Cluster	Iteration	Attack Category					No. of attacks detected	% of attack detection
		Normal	DOS	Probe	R2L	U2R		
1	1	172	62	59	3	5	301	1.194824
	2	12459	903	457	173	10	14002	55.581137
	3	140	108	3171	4	0	3423	13.587647
	4	28	8	33	3	0	72	0.285805
2	1	26	857	1037	1	0	1921	7.625437
	2	570	1174	1392	11	0	3147	12.492061
	3	12735	897	546	192	10	14380	57.081613
	4	51	1264	8283	10	0	9608	38.139092
3	1	2400	798	7801	187	4	11190	44.418863
	2	91	1	17	23	0	132	0.523976
	3	242	28	146	2	1	419	1.663226
	4	12444	867	366	188	9	13874	55.073039
4	1	10852	572	337	17	2	11780	46.760876
	2	330	211	7368	1	1	7911	31.402826
	3	333	1256	5371	10	0	6970	27.667513
	4	927	150	552	7	2	1638	6.50206

TABLE 7. Results of Fuzzy Possibilistic C-Means for NSL-KDD 20 Percent Dataset with 28 Features

Cluster	Iteration	Attack Category					No. of attacks detected	% of attack detection
		Normal	DOS	Probe	R2L	U2R		
1	1	670	821	81	113	1	1686	6.692601
	2	12414	838	271	174	5	13702	54.390283
	3	674	687	367	10	0	1738	6.899016
	4	398	505	292	10	0	1205	4.783265
2	1	3838	528	6142	15	3	10526	41.783106
	2	145	1	3	3	1	153	0.607336
	3	12672	903	550	193	10	14328	56.875198
	4	400	35	133	4	1	573	2.274532
3	1	51	1	1892	19	6	1969	7.815973
	2	26	104	8335	3	0	8468	33.613846
	3	56	699	8317	4	0	9076	36.027310
	4	12600	885	507	190	10	14192	56.335345
4	1	8891	939	1119	61	1	11011	43.708320
	2	865	1346	625	28	5	2869	11.388536
	3	48	0	0	1	1	50	0.198476
	4	52	864	8302	4	0	9222	36.606859

Table 7 shows the maximum percentage of attack detection by Fuzzy POSSIBILISTIC C-Means Clustering Algorithm for NSL-KDD 20 percent Dataset with 28 features is 56.88%, which is detected for Cluster-2.

TABLE 8. Percentage of Attacks Detected from NSL-KDD 20 Percent Pre-Processed Data using 28 Features by Fuzzy Possibilistic C-Means

Cluster	Iteration 1	Iteration 2	Iteration 3	Iteration 4
1	6.692601	54.390283	6.899016	4.783265
2	41.783106	0.607336	56.875198	2.274532
3	7.815973	33.613846	36.027310	56.335345
4	43.708320	11.388536	0.198476	36.606859

Table 8 shows that the maximum number of attack is detected in Cluster-2 at 3rd iteration and the percentage of

attack detection is 56.88%. The graphical illustration is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Percentage of attack detection for NSL-KDD 20 Percent dataset with 28 features using Fuzzy Possibilistic C-Means.

Table 9 shows the percentage of attack detection for Fuzzy C-Means and Fuzzy Possibilistic C-Means clustering algorithms. The maximum number of attack is detected in each cluster using Fuzzy Possibilistic C-Means clustering algorithm in comparison with Fuzzy C-Means clustering algorithm.

TABLE 9. Percentage of Attack Detection in Different Clusters using Fuzzy C-Means and Fuzzy Possibilistic C-Means Algorithms for NSL-KDD 20 Percent Dataset using 28 Features

Cluster	Existing [5]	Fuzzy Possibilistic C-Means	% Improved
1	45.95%	54.39%	8.44%
2	45.94%	56.88%	10.94%
3	45.95%	56.34%	10.39%
4	45.95%	43.71%	-2.24%

Fig. 2. Comparison of Fuzzy C-Means and Fuzzy Possibilistic C-Means algorithm for anomaly attack detection using NSL-KDD 20 percent dataset with 28 features

VI. CONCLUSION

Intrusion is an attempt to use computer system resources without privilege, resulting in accidental damage. Detecting intrusion means any mechanism that detects infiltration behavior. Intrusion Detection System (IDS) monitors its suspicious behavior against network traffic and security.

This paper presents an evaluation of data mining based Fuzzy C-Means Clustering and Fuzzy possibilistic C-Means Clustering algorithm over the NSL-KDD dataset to detect the major attack categories i.e. DoS, R2L, U2R and Probe. It is observed that maximum of 56.88% attack is detected by Fuzzy possibilistic C-Means clustering algorithm whereas with Fuzzy C-Means algorithm; maximum of 45.95% attack is detected for the NSL-KDD dataset with 28 features. So, it can be concluded that Fuzzy possibilistic C-Means algorithm can be used competently for network attack detection.

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